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**ADDIS ABABA UNIVERSITY COLLEGE OF EDUCATION
DEPARTMENT OF EDUCATIONAL PLANNING
AND MANAGEMENT.**

**THE PRACTICES AND CHALLENGES OF SCHOOL
LEADERSHIP IN THE SECONDARY SCHOOLS
OF BOLE SUBCITY**

BY

DEMELASH MISGANA

MAY, 2018 G.C

ADDIS ABABA, ETHIOPIA.

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**A THESIS SUBMITTED IN PARTIAL FULFILLMENT OF
DEGREE OF MASTER OF ART IN EDUCATIONAL
LEADERSHIP AND MANAGEMENT**

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ABSTRACT

The purpose of the study was to assess the practices of school leadership and the challenges that school leaders face in performing their duties in Secondary Schools of Bole sub city. The study employed a descriptive survey design. Principals, vice principals and supervisors were selected using purposive sampling. Semi structured interview was also utilized to substantiate the data gained through the questionnaires. Both primary and secondary sources were used. The primary sources of this study were principals, vice principals, supervisors and teachers of the selected schools. On the other hand secondary sources were relevant documents of the schools in the study area. To gather the necessary data three types of data collection instruments namely questionnaire consisting of closed ended item, structured interview and document analysis were used descriptive approach such as percentage, frequency, mean, standard deviation and grand mean were utilized to analyze the data .The qualitative data obtained through interview was analyzed using themes. The results of the study revealed that all school principals have qualification in school leadership but some of school vice principals involved in leading the school without having prior qualification in school leadership and trainings. The study concluded that principals are less effective in their leadership due to problem of working with parents and community, work overload and lack of sharing the problems of school leadership by higher officials. Finally, the point of the recommended that qualified secondary school principals and vice principals be assigned it is on the basis of their experience and academic merits, providing in-service and pre-service training and build productive relationships with parents and the wider community.

ACRONYMS

MOE: Ministry Of Education

USA: United State Of America

A.D: Anno Domini

UK: United Kingdom

B.A: Bachelor Art

B.S.C: Bachelor Of Science

SIP: School Improvement Program

GEQIP: General Education Quality Improvement Program

CPD: Continuous Professional Development

OECD: Organization For Economic Co-Operation And Development/

CHAPTER ONE

INTRODUCTION

This chapter provides the background of the study, statement of the problem, objectives of the Study, significance of the study, delimitations of the study, limitations of the study, definition of terms and organization of the study.

1.1 BACKGROUND OF THE STUDY

Leadership is defined differently by different authors. House (1996) Leadership is “the ability of an individual to influence, motivate, and enable others to contribute toward the effectiveness and success of the organization.” Terry (1960) defines leadership as an activity of influencing people to strive willingly for group goals. To Clark (1992), leadership is an activity an influence process in which an individual gains the trust and commitment of others and without recourse to formal position or authority, moves the group to the accomplishment of one or more tasks. Leadership involves influence, it occurs among people, those people intentionally desire significance changes and the changes reflect purposes shared by leaders and followers.

School leadership has become a priority in education policy agendas internationally. It plays a key role in improving school outcomes by influencing the motivations and capacities of teachers, as well as the school climate and environment. Effective school leadership is essential to improve the efficiency and equity of schooling. Leadership effectiveness is a key factor for all organizational success. Yukl (2010) explains the common indicators of effective leadership as the extent to which the performance of the team or organizational unit is enhanced and the attainment of goals is facilitated; follower attitudes and perceptions of the leader and the leader’s contribution to the quality of group processes, as perceived by followers or by outside observers.

Sammons et al. (1997) and Harris (2001) make clear that many studies indicate, in educational institution it was found that leadership does make differences to student outcomes and institutional activities. The importance of leadership in this regard has been demonstrated in both research and practice. Tschannen and Garries (2004) affirmed that in these times, it is widely

accepted that good educational leaders are the cornerstones of good educational institutions, and without their leadership effort, educational institutions cannot be successful. In light of this, Johnson and Snyder (1986) recommended that school leaders particularly principals are key factors in the school's attempt to alter achievement norms and strong instructional leadership is one of the most important determinants of all school activities associated with school effectiveness. Contemporary scholars such as Duke (2006) have observed that the lack of effective leadership in schools lowers students' achievement because the absence of quality leadership often results in ill-adapted school organization and programs. It also leads to unstable and difficult staffing, students' negative attitudes to academic work and discipline, an unhealthy school system and climate, and non-cooperation of parents and community.

The principal is the leading professional in the school .The major role of the principal is providing professional leadership and management for the school. Lots of research state that Principals must establish a culture that promotes excellence, equality and high expectation of all peoples and provides vision, leadership and directions, and are staffed predominantly by professional.

(Leithwood & Riehl, 2003) the role of leadership is to produce change in students, change that occurs in knowledge, attitudes, skills and behavior. The responsibility of the principal is to ensure that students learn and to lead schools. Of course, leading schools is complex work. The principal of a school is a planner, director, controller, coordinator, organizer, adviser and a problem-solver Maduabum, (2002). The school leader ensures student learning by managing the organization, operations, and resources for a safe, efficient learning environment. This has implication for the nature of management in educational organization, because professional seek a measure of control over their working enrollment in professional organization, then there is an authority of expertise which may come in to conflict with professional authorities.

As to Musazi (1988) inadequate leadership in at the school level is the one that adversely affect the progress of education. Because of success in any educational institutions depend significantly on effective and sound leadership.

Generally the presence of effective school leaders, positive school climate, and positive attitude of teachers can directly or indirectly influence school performance and student's achievement. A

school as an organization is influenced by its principalship (Andy, 2010; Everard et al, 2004; Nigel et al, 2003 and Philip, 2005).

Therefore, investigating the currently existing leadership practice and challenges of school leadership has been central focus of this study.

1.2. STATEMENT OF THE PROBLEM

A school system is one of the public institutions having its own specific goals and objectives to be achieved and such task is given to school leaders. Therefore, effective leadership is at the core of every successful organization (Sergiovanni as cited in Temesgen, 2011). Moreover, effective leadership within the school is collegial, student-centered and teacher focused, promoting collective responsibility for change agent (MoE, 2010).

The role of school leadership is very essential and hence it is non - negotiable as it is one of the major factors that identify successful schools from unsuccessful ones. The school leadership faces many problems as the school is operating in affinity complex environment. In this respect, Maurer.R (1991) argued that educational leaders inevitably find themselves facing many challenges, uncertainties and ambiguities in their education practice and management.

School leaders need to have the theoretical knowledge, skill and adequate experiences in school leadership so as to play active and effective leadership role in the school. It is also stated that principals should have a profile of possession of various training on school leadership and management (MoE, 1999). Therefore, according to the Ministry of Education the principals who are going to be assigned as principals of the school must have the necessary understanding, ability and significant preparation for school leadership.

As criteria a blue print of teacher development program (MoE, 2008) has stated that the academic qualification required for the secondary school principalship is a master's degree. Regarding the area of specialization of principals a blue print of teacher's development program (MoE, 2007) has stated that the school principals need to have adequate knowledge, skills and attitude in the area of educational administration. I also agree with the statement stated above, however, there are some specialized principals in the study area. Therefore there is a gap of policy Implementation in selected sampling schools. The ability to perform technical

management; building school culture an attractiveness of school compound; ability to create participatory decision making and school management for teachers and students; ability to create Orderly school environment by clarifying duties and responsibilities; selection and recruitment skills and ability to communicate with different stakeholders.

Moreover, the principal personality, vision, extent of commitment, human relation skill's etc. can serve to constrain/hamper the exercise of leadership. Strengthening this idea, Gorten(1983) states that if the principal doesn't possess the appropriate personal qualities needed, the absence of these characteristics can be self-constrain out leadership responsibilities properly.

Secondary school leaders, in Ethiopia, are expected to be trained in educational leadership for the activities such as, planning, supervision, research work, professional development, provision of instructional materials and evaluation to achieve the objective of education and training policy (MOE, 2002).

On the contrary the reality on the ground showed that school leadership has different problems particularly at the secondary schools. Different studies have been conducted on some related topics, Addisu Chonde, conducted a study on practice and challenges of instructional leadership in selected preparatory schools of hadiya zone, SNNPS, his focus was instructional leadership part of principal, Bogale Tolera (2014) also did his study on "an assessment of the role and practices of School principals as instructional leaders in secondary schools of south west shoa Zone". Focus on role and practice of school principals as instructional leadership. Still Roza Belew (2016), selamawit Getasew (2016) and Alemu 2015) all are focused on instructional leadership.

Therefore most of the researchers mentioned above conducted their study on the issues of instructional leadership but the researcher need to study both instructional and administrative activities those are takes place in the schools.

Accordingly, the main intension of this study to assess the practice and challenges of school leadership in bole sub city are carry out their leadership responsibilities in participatory manner starting from goal and vision setting, strategic planning up to the realization of vision and achieving of plan and goals.

In view of the fact stated above, the present studies therefore, attempt to assess the practices and challenges of school leadership in the secondary schools of Bole sub city based on the following basic questions:

- I. What are the practices of educational leadership in secondary schools of Bole sub city?
- II. What are the challenges that secondary school leaders in Bole sub city encountered in their leadership activities?
- III. What are the possible solutions that alleviate the main challenges school leaders' face?

1.3. OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

1.3.1. GENERAL OBJECTIVES

The major objectives of this study is to assess the practices and challenges of school Leadership in secondary schools of Bole sub city.

1.3.2. SPECIFIC OBJECTIVES

The specific objectives are to:

- i. Identify the current practices of school leadership in secondary schools of Bole sub city.
- ii. Identify the major challenges the school leadership in leading the school.
- iii. Suggest how principals become effective in school leadership.

1.4. SIGNIFICANCE OF THE STUDY

The study was concerned with the current practices and problems of school leadership of secondary schools in Bole sub city. It will assume that this research would be significant to wide range of educational institutions. The result of the study possibly would help the following stake holders in the educational system of the country.

Leaders of educational institutions would get some ideas on how to become effective in their leadership practices, and they could realize challenging factors that hinder school principal's

from leading schools in effective way and take relevant or appropriate measures that will minimize the hindrances principals' effectiveness, and enhance quality of school leadership.

The study may contribute additional information to the existing finding by revealing the practical experiences in the world. Besides, it can be used as a reference material for further studies in the area.

1.5 DELIMITATION OF THE STUDY

According to Ayalew and Seyoum (1999) "...to carry out any research work it should be important to delimit the study to a manageable size". Based on this theoretical base, the study is delimited to the leadership practices and challenges of school leadership in secondary schools of Bole sub city of Addis Ababa. Mainly in five districts that include seven secondary schools (9 – 10, 9 – 12, and 11 – 12). As a major focus of the study, it is delimited to current leadership practices chiefly required of educational school principals. Considerable attention is given to the main function of principals' practice and challenges in the school leadership.

1.6 LIMITATIONS OF THE STUDY

It is known that any research cannot be totally free from limitation. The following limitations were also observed in the study.

- I. Most of secondary school principals, vice principals, teachers and district supervisors are busy and do not have enough time to respond to questionnaires and interview
- II. Some of them who have enough time were also reluctant to fill in and return the questionnaire as per the required time
- III. Lack of recent and relevant literature on the topic, especially on Ethiopian condition. However the researcher overcomes these limitations by devoting his time, consuming his finance and searching materials from different universities.

1.7. DEFINITION OF THE KEY TERMS

1. **Challenge:** any condition or phenomena that hinders school leaders' activities in the school.

2. **Leader:** is a person who leads a group of people, especially the head of a country, organization etc. A leader in a group of people or an organization is the person who is control of it or in charge of it.
3. **Leadership:** The process of influencing the activities of an individual or group in effort towards goal achievement in a given situation (Krug, 1992)
4. **Organization:** a group of people who form a business, club etc together in order to achieve a particular form.
5. **Practice:** activities that are carried in the school by the school leaders to improve school success..
6. **Principal:** the name refers to the administrative head and professional leader in charge of secondary schools (Good: 1973: 436)
7. **School leader:** Refers to instructional leaders namely, principals, supervisors, department heads, unit leaders, and senior teachers that take part in the leadership of the teaching-learning and management (Sergiovanni, 2001)
8. **Secondary schools:** the second Educational level from 9 – 12 sub divided in to two cycles (1st cycle) 9-10 and (2nd cycle) preparatory studies (11 –12) in Ethiopia (MoE, 1994).
9. **Sub cities:** An intermediate administration level between Addis Ababa City administration and district administration.
10. **Supervisor:** A professional personnel responsible for the promotion, development, maintenance and improvement of instruction (Good, 1973).

1.8. ORGANIZATION OF THE STUDY

This paper has five parts. The first chapter deals with the background of the study, statement of the problem, objectives of the study, Significant of the study, Delimitation of the study, limitation of the study, Definition of key Terms, and organization of the study. Chapter two presents review of the related literature. The research design and methodology and the data

presentation, analysis and interpretation are treated under chapter three and four respectively. The last chapter deals with the summary, conclusion and recommendations.

CHAPTER TWO

REVIEW OF THE RELATED LITERATURE

This chapter presents related literature that helps to enrich the study. The literature deals with the concept of leadership, theories of leadership, leadership styles, leadership skills, school leadership, the role of school principals finally it treats the challenges faced by school principals.

2.1 THE CONCEPT OF LEADERSHIP

Leadership is considered to be the most essential to the successful functioning of many aspects of school. Leadership researchers have defined leadership in many different ways. For example (Bennis, 1959) defined leadership as the process by which an agent induces a subordinate to behave in a desired manner. (Roach & Behling, 1986) defined leadership as the process of influencing an organized group toward accomplishment its goals. Hemphill & Coons (cited in Yukl, 2008) define leadership as it is the behavior of an individual directing the activities of a group toward a shared vision.

Beare, et.al (1989) also defined that leadership is viewed as a process that includes influencing the task objective and strategies of a group or organization; influencing people in the organization to implement the strategies and achieve the objectives, influencing group maintenance and identification, and influencing the culture of the organization. Additionally, leadership can be defined as a complex social process, rooted in aspects of values, skills, knowledge as well as ways of thinking of both leaders and followers.

On the other hand, Hoy and Miskel (2000) assert that leadership should be defined broadly as a special process in which a member of a group or organization influences the interpretation of internal and external events, the choice of goals or desired outcomes, organization of work activities individual motivation and abilities, power relation and shared orientations. According to Grant R.M (2003), Leadership is the process of inspiring others to work hard to accomplish important tasks. It builds commitment and enthusiasm needed for people to apply their talents to help accomplish plan. Furthermore, some scholars highlight leadership as change or moving forward.

2.2 THEORIES OF LEADERSHIP

Theories are a cornerstone that helps to understand facts and worlds in coherent and organized assumptions. There are three separated leadership theories: trait, behavioral and contingency theories of leadership. Each of them incorporates several distinct aspects of leadership (Holt, 1998). The perspectives of different scholars toward each cornerstone or theories of leadership will be described below.

2.2.1 TRAIT THEORY OF LEADERSHIP

This theory is also known as the “great man theory” because according to this theory leaders are born and not made (Kreitner and Kinicki, 2001:533) and Morphet et.al (1982:99). Similarly, Stoner et al (2002) stated the characteristics of leaders as “Leader share certain in born personality traits”. According to these theories leaders are portrayed as heroic, mythic and destined to rise to leadership when needed. People who possess those inherent qualities and traits are better suited to leadership. (Stogdill1974) identified the following traits and skills as critical to leaders:

Traits: Adaptable to situations, alert to school environment, ambitious and achievement oriented, assertive, cooperative and decisive e.t.c.

Skills: Clever, (intelligent) conceptually skilled, creative, diplomatic and tactful, fluent in speaking knowledgeable about group task, and etc.

From the above notions, it may possible to say that there will be personal (inborn) characteristics of school leaders that might help to judge whether they are effective or not. Furthermore, according to the theory effective leaders have their own distinguishing inborn characteristics that will make them effective.

2.2.2 BEHAVIORAL THEORY OF LEADERSHIP

Behavioral studies of leadership aim to identify behaviors that differentiate leaders from non leaders (Robbins, 1998). This theory of leadership is based upon the belief that great leaders are made, not born. Also this theory of leadership focuses to the leader behavior in the context of the organization. Leaders can affect their organizational performance by employing various styles or

behaviors that fit their organizational setting: autocratic, democratic, and laissez-faire styles of leadership (Carlson, 1996).

In contrast to trait theory, it also believes that a leader did not seem to have a particular set of distinguished trait rather leadership behavior can be developed by training and through active interaction of individual with ever-changing organizational environments. Behavioral theory focus on leadership function and leadership styles of the leader (Stoner et al, 2002).

As we have seen from this theory, being a leader or effective school leader will be made through careful and well designed training of individuals with required effective leadership behaviors that may help the leader to utilize those behaviors according to the organizational situations. In other words, leaders are not born rather made to fit the situation of the organization. On the top of this idea, whatever the style applied by the leaders highly structured or highly employee consideration in the continuum, participative style of leadership will generate systematically better performance and greater job satisfaction than other alternatives (Holt, 1998).

Therefore, school leaders, according to the proponents of this theory, should have to be trained with appropriate elements of leadership through different mechanisms that demands recent skills to deal with the organizational/ institutional context. Through this process the role of school leaders will be enhanced to bring school effectiveness through participative and collaborative decision making process in all school concern.

2.2.3 CONTINGENCY THEORY OF LEADERSHIP

Contingency theory of leadership was introduced by Fred Fiedler in 1967 which gives or stipulates the concept of no-single leadership style works well in all situation of the organization (Holt, 1998). This theory of leadership focus on particular variables related to the environment that might determine which particular style of leadership is best suited for the situation. To strengthen this idea, unlike to trait and behavioral theory, the effectiveness of particular leadership style practiced by a leader might be influenced by different factors such as task requirements, peer's expectation and behavior, employees' characteristics, expectations and behavior; and organizational policy and culture (Stoner et al, 2002). Similarly, for better effective school leadership practice Ayalew (1991: 33 – 34) denoted that “The primary managerial role is to maximize the congruency of the organization and its environment and into

the various sub-systems. The appropriate fit between the organization and its environment and appropriate internal organizational design will lead to greater effectiveness, efficiency, and participant satisfaction. Thus, schools as they are operating under the domains of continuous and perplexing internal and external environment, they need to have a better and consistence reconciliation with the environments through effective school leadership.

2.3. LEADERSHIP STYLES

A leadership style here refers to the broad approach adopted by a leader. A leader's style of leadership is often based up on a leader's own belief, personality, experience, working environment, and the situation at the time. Some leaders work within one leadership style. Others are more flexible and can adapt their style of leadership to meet the needs of different situations. Leadership styles are the patterns of behavior used by leaders in attempting to influence group members and make decision regarding the mission, strategy, and operations of group activities.

According to Clark (2000) leadership style is the manner and approach in which a leader provides direction, implements plans, and motivates people so as to achieve organizational goals. This therefore means that leadership style and the effectiveness of interactions between leaders and their subordinates are important determinants of team success in any hierarchical organization .However, leadership styles vary from one institution to another and it is essential to mention that no two leaders can administer and lead their institutions in the same way.

2.3.1 AUTOCRATIC LEADERSHIP

Autocratic leadership is an extreme form of transactional leadership, where leaders have a lot of power over their people. Staff and team members have little opportunity to make suggestions, even if these would be in the team's or the organization's best interest. The benefit of autocratic leadership is that it's incredibly efficient. Decisions are made quickly, and work gets done efficiently. The downside is that most people resent being treated this way. Therefore, autocratic leadership can often lead to high levels of absenteeism and high staff turnover. However, the style can be effective for some routine and unskilled jobs: in these situations, the advantages of control may outweigh the disadvantages. Autocratic leadership is often best used in crises, when decisions must be made quickly and without dissent. For instance, the military often uses an

autocratic leadership style; top commanders are responsible for quickly making complex decisions, which allows troops to focus their attention and energy on performing their allotted tasks and missions.

2.3.2 BUREAUCRATIC LEADERSHIP

Bureaucratic leaders work "by the book." They follow rules rigorously, and ensure that their people follow procedures precisely. This is an appropriate leadership style for work involving serious safety risks (such as working with machinery, with toxic substances, or at dangerous heights) or where large sums of money are involved. Bureaucratic leadership is also useful in organizations where employees do routine tasks (as in manufacturing). The downside of this leadership style is that it's ineffective in teams and organizations that rely on flexibility, creativity, or innovation. Much of the time, bureaucratic leaders achieve their position because of their ability to conform to and uphold rules, not because of their qualifications or expertise. This can cause resentment when team members don't value their expertise or advice.

2.3.3 CHARISMATIC LEADERSHIP

A charismatic leadership style can resemble transformational leadership because these leaders inspire enthusiasm in their teams and are energetic in motivating others to move forward. This ability to create excitement and commitment is an enormous benefit. The difference between charismatic leaders and transformational leaders lies in their intention. Transformational leaders want to transform their teams and organizations. Charismatic leaders are often focused on themselves, and may not want to change anything. The downside to charismatic leaders is that they can believe more in themselves than in their teams. This can create the risk that a project or even an entire organization might collapse if the leader leaves. A charismatic leader might believe that he/she can do no wrong, even when others are warning her about the path she's on; and this feeling of invincibility can ruin a team or an organization. Also, in the followers' eyes, success is directly connected to the presence of the charismatic leader. As such, charismatic leadership carries great responsibility, and it needs a long-term commitment from the leader.

2.3.4 DEMOCRATIC/PARTICIPATIVE LEADERSHIP

Democratic leaders make the final decisions, but they include team members in the decision-making process. They encourage creativity, and team members are often highly engaged in projects and decisions. There are many benefits of democratic leadership. Team members tend to have high job satisfaction and are productive because they're more involved in decisions. This style also helps develop people's skills. Team members feel in control of their destiny, so they're motivated to work hard by more than just a financial reward. Because participation takes time, this approach can slow decision-making, but the result is often good. The approach can be most suitable when working as a team is essential, and when quality is more important than efficiency or productivity. The downside of democratic leadership is that it can often hinder situations where speed or efficiency is essential. For instance, during a crisis, a team can waste valuable time gathering people's input. Another downside is that some team members might not have the knowledge or expertise to provide high quality input.

2.3.5 LAISSEZ-FAIRE LEADERSHIP

This French phrase means "leave it be," and it describes leaders who allow their people to work on their own. This type of leadership can also occur naturally, when managers don't have sufficient control over their work and their people. Laissez-faire leaders may give their teams' complete freedom to do their work and set their own deadlines. They provide team support with resources and advice, if needed, but otherwise don't get involved. This leadership style can be effective if the leader monitors performance and gives feedback to team members regularly. It is most likely to be effective when individual team members are experienced, skilled, self-starters. The main benefit of laissez-faire leadership is that giving team members so much autonomy can lead to high job satisfaction and increased productivity. The downside is that it can be damaging if team members don't manage their time well or if they don't have the knowledge, skills, or motivation to do their work effectively.

2.3.6 PEOPLE-ORIENTED/RELATIONS-ORIENTED LEADERSHIP

With people-oriented leadership, leaders are totally focused on organizing, supporting, and developing the people on their teams. This is a participatory style and tends to encourage good

teamwork and creative collaboration. This is the opposite of task-oriented leadership. people-oriented leaders treat everyone on the team equally. They're friendly and approachable, they pay attention to the welfare of everyone in the group, and they make themselves available whenever team members need help or the benefit of this leadership style is that people-oriented leaders create teams that everyone wants to be part of. Team members are often more productive and willing to take risks, because they know that the leader will provide support if they need it. The downside is that some leaders can take this approach too far; they may put the development of their team above tasks or project directives.

2.3.7 SERVANT LEADERSHIP

This term, created by Robert Greenleaf in the 1970s, describes a leader often not formally recognized as such. When someone at any level within an organization leads simply by meeting the needs of the team, he or she can be described as a "servant leader." Servant leaders often lead by example. They have high integrity and lead with generosity. In many ways, servant leadership is a form of democratic leadership because the whole team tends to be involved in decision making. However, servant leaders often "lead from behind," preferring to stay out of the limelight and letting their team accept recognition for their hard work. Supporters of the servant leadership model suggest that it's a good way to move ahead in a world where values are increasingly important, and where servant leaders can achieve power because of their values, ideals, and ethics. This is an approach that can help to create a positive corporate culture and can lead to high morale among team members. However, other people believe that in competitive leadership situations, people who practice servant leadership can find themselves left behind by leaders using other leadership styles. This leadership style also takes time to apply correctly: it's ill-suited in situations where you have to make quick decisions or meet tight deadlines. Although you can use servant leadership in many situations, it's often most practical in politics, or in positions where leaders are elected to serve a team, committee, organization, or community.

2.3.8 TASK-ORIENTED LEADERSHIP

Task-oriented leaders focus only on getting the job done and can be autocratic. They actively define the work and the roles required, put structures in place, and plan, organize, and monitor work. These leaders also perform other key tasks, such as creating and maintaining standards for

performance. The benefit of task-oriented leadership is that it ensures that deadlines are met, and it's especially useful for team members who don't manage their time well. However, because task-oriented leaders don't tend to think much about their team's well-being, this approach can suffer many of the flaws of autocratic leadership, including causing motivation and retention problems.

2.3.9 TRANSACTIONAL LEADERSHIP

This leadership style starts with the idea that team members agree to obey their leader when they accept a job. The "transaction" usually involves the organization paying team members in return for their effort and compliance. The leader has a right to "punish" team members if their work doesn't meet an appropriate standard. Although this might sound controlling and paternalistic, transactional leadership offers some benefits. For one, this leadership style clarifies everyone's roles and responsibilities. Another benefit is that, because transactional leadership judges team members on performance, people who are ambitious or who are motivated by external rewards including compensation often thrive. The downside of this leadership style is that team members can do little to improve their job satisfaction. It can feel stifling, and it can lead to high staff turnover. Transactional leadership is really a type of management, not a true leadership style, because the focus is on short-term tasks. It has serious limitations for knowledge-based or creative work. However, it can be effective in other situations.

2.3.10 TRANSFORMATIONAL LEADERSHIP

As we discussed earlier in this article, transformation leadership is often the best leadership style to use in business situations. Transformational leaders are inspiring because they expect the best from everyone on their team as well as themselves. This leads to high productivity and engagement from everyone in their team. The downside of transformational leadership is that while the leader's enthusiasm is passed onto the team, he or she can need to be supported by "detail people." That's why, in many organizations, both transactional and transformational leadership styles are useful. Transactional leaders (or managers) ensure that routine work is done reliably, while transformational leaders look after initiatives that add new value. It's also important to use other leadership styles when necessary. This will depend on the people you're leading and the situation that you're in.

2.4 LEADERSHIP SKILLS OF LEADERS

Effective leadership depends on three basic personal skills: technical, human, and conceptual. Although all three skills are important for leaders, the importance of each skill varies between management levels. At lower management levels, technical and human skills are most important. For middle managers, the three different skills are equally important. At upper management levels, conceptual and human skills are most important, and technical skills become less important. Leaders are more effective when their skills match their management level.

Thus the skill of the principal is referring to his/her over all abilities to exercise the authority and power equivalent to his/her position expertly to bring about effective changes in the school he/she assigned. From this perspective, principals having the necessary skills of lacking of them could have a positive or negative impact in the attainment of the educational goals of the school.

2.4.1 TECHNICAL SKILLS

Technical skills include knowledge about methods, processes, and equipment for conducting the specialized activities of the leader's organizational unit. Technical skills also include factual knowledge about the organization (rules, structure, leadership systems, employee characteristics), and knowledge about the organization's products and services (technical specifications, strengths, and limitations). This type of knowledge is acquired by a combination of formal education, training, and job experience.

According to Koontz and Wehrich (1988:323), „technical skills are the knowledge and proficiency in activities involving methods, procedures and processes“. A technical skill is the ability of applying knowledge, methods and techniques that are necessary for the performance of the given tasks (Katz, 1974).

Acquisition of technical knowledge is facilitated by a good memory for details and the ability to learn technical material quickly. Effective leaders are able to obtain information and ideas from many sources and store it away in their memory for use when they need it. Leaders who supervise the work of others need extensive knowledge of the techniques and equipment used by subordinates to perform the work. Technical knowledge of products and processes is necessary

to plan and organize work operations, to direct and train subordinates with specialized activities, and to monitor and evaluate their performance.

According to Bell (1992) technical tasks are those, which are specific to primary purpose of the school. The primary purpose of the school is the education of its people. Since the most important and major purpose of the school is teaching learning activities, principals should be competent in their specialized areas. School principals need to possess adequate knowledge of methods, procedures process and techniques that could be applied in interpreting the curriculum by all teachers.

Technical skills are generally associated with the ability to use tools, procedures, and techniques of specialized areas. Therefore, school principals as leading practitioners should be able to be competent in technical skills such as in scheduling, managing curriculum, and supervisory activities.

2.4.2 INTERPERSONAL SKILLS

Interpersonal (or social) skills include knowledge about human behavior and group processes, ability to understand the feelings, attitudes, and motives of others, and ability to communicate clearly and persuasively. Specific types of interpersonal skills such as empathy, social insight, charm, tact and diplomacy, persuasiveness, and oral communication ability are essential to develop and maintain cooperative relationships with subordinates, superiors, peers, and outsiders. Someone who understands people and is charming, tactful, and diplomatic will have more cooperative relationships than a person who is insensitive and offensive.

Interpersonal skills are essential for influencing people. Empathy is the ability to understand another person's motives, values, and emotions, and social insight is the ability to understand what types of behavior are socially acceptable in a particular situation.

Interpersonal skills also enhance the effectiveness of relationship-oriented behaviors. Strong interpersonal skills help a manager listen in an attentive, sympathetic, and nonjudgmental way to somebody with a personal problem, complaint, or criticism.

Interpersonal skill is one of the most important aspects of managerial skills of principals.

An interpersonal skill refers to the school executive's ability to work effectively and efficiently with other people on a one-to-one basis and in-group setting.

If good interpersonal skills are to be prevailing among the school personnel, principals must have the desire to see the group must reduce conflict. In a position in which success depends upon working through others, friendliness must have an outgoing quality. Hence in order to work with and through people, principals are required to acquaint themselves with the knowledge of what motivates the staff, how to work cooperatively with them and how to create common networks in the school so as to give fresh impetus to the provision of instructional to clients. Therefore, in order to be effective in the human relation aspects of school, principals should be competent in applying the concept of motivation, seek to exert the relevant style leadership and need to be good communicators.

2.4.3 CONCEPTUAL SKILLS

In general terms, conceptual (or cognitive) skills involve good judgment, foresight, intuition, creativity, and the ability to find meaning and order in ambiguous, uncertain events. Specific conceptual skills that can be measured with aptitude tests include analytical ability, logical thinking, concept formation, inductive reasoning, and deductive reasoning. Cognitive complexity involves a combination of these specific skills and is defined as the ability to utilize cues to make distinctions and develop categories for classifying things, as well as the ability to identify complex relationships and develop creative solutions to problems.

A person with low cognitive complexity sees things in simplistic black and white terms and has difficulty in seeing how many diverse elements fit together to make a meaningful whole. A person with high cognitive complexity is able to see many shades of gray and is able to identify complex patterns of relationships and predict future events from current trends.

Conceptual skills include the school executive's ability to see the school, the district, and the total educational program as a whole. The skill includes the effective mapping of interdependence for each of the components of the school as an organization.

Conceptual skills, therefore, enable organizational leaders to see the overall features of organization to understand interrelationship, interaction and interdependence of various components of a system. In terms of leadership it means sensitivity to the organization.

Rue and Byars (1992) stated that, managerial skills are so closely interrelated that in practice that is difficult to determine where one begins and another ends. However, it is generally agreed that supervisory management needs more technical skills than managers at higher levels. Interpersonal skills are essential to effective management at all levels. Conceptual skills become increasingly important as a person moves up the managerial hierarchy. Similarly, Katz (1974) suggested that although each of these skills are important to school executive's at all hierarchical level, technical skills are most important to administrators at lower levels, and conceptual skills are more important to those at the upper levels. The emphasis on technical and conceptual may vary with management level, but interpersonal skills are the common denominator that appears to be crucial at all levels.

2. 5. SCHOOL LEADERSHIP

Leadership has very important impacts on the quality of the school organization and on students' outcome. This is applicable with the meaning of leadership since leadership is all about organizational advancement. Particularly, it is all about organizing the organization (school) to achieve shared goals. The goal of school leadership is school improvement. Indeed, school leadership is an essential part for school effectiveness in order to prepare students to reach their future success. (Leithwood, Day, Sammons, Harris & Hopkins, 2006).

In addition, school leadership, an effective one, has been an important groundwork for school improvement and student achievement. (Hariri, et al., 2012 Raihani, 2008) This could have happened because based on most leadership researchers found that school leadership facilitates students' achievement through the provision of better school conditions (Rai-hani, 2008).

According to Leithwood et al., (2006) in order to improve the school and students' outcomes, the leader, in this case, the school's principal needs to involve and engage all school elements. The schools elements consist of teachers and school stakeholders. School principals need to be able to motivate and improve the conditions of all school elements. To be successful, therefore, requires principals to have cognitive and emotive qualities, strategies and skills.

Furthermore, Hariri et al., (2012) advise that school leadership should not be separated from the principal's decision-making styles and teachers' job achievement. Decision-making and job achievements are important elements of leadership. By understanding decision-making styles will encourage principals to perform well in making a decision. As a result, effective decision making by principals will effectively assist teachers to meet their job satisfaction.

Moreover, Fullan (2001) found out the evidence of school improvements since 1990s. The school improvement involves principals who are (1) accommodative, (2) focus on student learning, (3) productive and (4) both pressure and support. Principals are expected to work together with parents, teachers and school stakeholders to stimulate action. (Fullan,2001)

Theoretically, instructional leadership is an important principle for the dynamic establishment of broader school leadership. This concept is determined by understanding the educational leaders who highly contribute on improving the students' learning outcomes. (Sofu et al.,2012)

2.5.1 PRINCIPALSHIP IN THE WORLD

A principal is" the administrative head and professional leader of high school"(Good, 1973:436) According to Monahan and Hengst(1982:293) and Murphy and (1995:13-14), the term principal is used in the united state of America which was originally derived from the phrase" principal teacher" head master or head mistress in the England is similar to principal in USA(Monahan and Hengst 1982), in Ethiopia, that the term" director" has been used to designate the same incumbent until the advent of Derg regime. After the equivalent term" principal" has been use. The principal is the official leader of a school the responsibility of whom being directing influencing and controlling the teaching learning process under his charge through, mainly, teachers; and is accountable for implementation of the education and training policy.

The development of principalship is firmly attached with the history of the principals in the United States of America. In the early history of American schooling there were no principals like that of today, school administration was not differentiated from teaching implying that everything was done by teacher.(Murphy,1995)

According to Monahan and Hengst and Murphy, As cities grow, schools increased in number and size and the number and complexity of educational tasks also increased with required

secured assistance that a specially designated person assumed responsibility for them. This person named as "principal teacher" continued to function in the class room but also served as the community head of the school.

Especially the adjectival connotation of principal was lost towards the end of 19th century of the need for more direction become evident. The principal teacher become more involved in machining operational decisions exercising control over daily management matters including guiding the work of teacher in each school. (Monaham and Hengst, 1982). Therefore, the preconditions for creation of principalship were the expansion of education as result of the growth of cities and the freeing of principal teachers from teaching.

Regarding the criteria for principal ship, for example, Rebore in MOE (2002) Amharic version, indicates that principalship in America is based on qualification level and special training in educational leadership. Another example is a Kenyan experience. Principalship in Kenya is obtained mainly based on the quality of work performance, advanced educational standard, at least three years of teaching experience, training in directorial inspection and good personality and social standing.

2.5.2 THE SCHOOL LEADERSHIPS IN ETHIOPIA

The history of Ethiopian education system traces its origin to the introduction of Christianity during the era of Ezana of Aksumite Empire, around fourth century A.D. Ethiopia for a very long time had found schools for the children of their adherents (Teshome, n.d cited in Wondimu, 2014). However, the western type of education system was formally introduced in to Ethiopia in 1908 with opening of Menilik Primary School at the capital city Addis Ababa (Wondimu, 2014). According to Ahmed, (2006) the history of school leader ship in Ethiopia was at its early age was dominated by foreign principals .In all government schools which were opened before and after Italian occupation, expatriates from France, Britain, Sweden, Canada, Egypt and India, were assigned as school principals. Late in 1941, after the restoration of independence, education was given high priority which resulted in opening of schools in different parts of the Ethiopia (Dessalegn, 2014).Because of the reason that there was no enough educated Ethiopians to teach and run schools, most of the teachers and principals in schools were from foreign countries such as UK, USA, Canada, Egypt and India (Wondimu, 2014).

In 1964, it was a turning point Ethiopians started to replace expatriates in which this new chapter of principal ship began with a supervising principal that such a person was in charged not only for a single school but also for the educational system of the community where the school was located (Teshome, cited in Dessalegn, 2014).

After 1960, it was known the Ethiopians who graduated with B.A / B.S.C Degree in any field were assigned as principals in schools by senior officials of Ministry of Education that the major selection requirements were educational level and work experience (MoE, 2002; Wondimu, 2014).

Since the formulation of new education and Training policy in 1994, Ethiopian Government has made different educational reforms like implementing the newly launched School Improvement Program (SIP). It is one of the components of the General Education Quality Improvement Program (GEQIP) (MoE, 2007; Wondimu, 2014). MoE (2007) cited in Rahel (2014) stated that the main focus of SIP in Ethiopia is to enhance student achievement by improving student learning and other conditions associated with in the teaching and learning process. The document also mentions that the need for SIP is to make schools accountable for parents, community and government to develop the responsibility and accountability of educational personnel's working at different level of the education system. From those educational personnel's, principals of schools play the fundamental role in making the schools accountable.

MoE (2007, in Wondimu, 2014) point out that SIP focuses on four major domains of the school namely: improving the teaching and learning, creating conducive learning environment, improving school leadership, and enhancing community participation in school affairs. The fundamental objectives of the school performances in the manual are harmonious with dimensions of instructional leadership (MoE, 2007; Wondimu, 2014).

Concerning leadership, Harris (2002, in Rahel, 2014) stated that it is about having vision and articulating, ordering priorities, getting others to go with you, reviewing what you are doing, and holding on to things you value. Harris et al, (2005) cited in Rahel (2014) mentioned that effective leadership (school leadership) assumes authority not to be located in the persons of the leader but can be dispersed within the school in between and among people by building collaborative cultures through generating positive relationship. This implies that improving

school leadership quality to enhance student achievement is critical element in school processes and that is why it is included in the school improvement program. The Ethiopian education and training policy (1994) cited in Wondimu (2014) stated that Educational management or leadership should be democratic, professional, coordinated, efficient, and effective.

2.6 THE ROLE OF SCHOOL PRINCIPALS

Principals play an important role as leaders of the school and they influence different functions within the schools with their behaviors, personal characteristics, and biases. The school principals perform a number of tasks and responsibilities in order to improve teaching and learning process. The leadership function of the school principals has two major dimensions. First, he/she serves as the chief administrative officer in the school and as an educational leader. In other words, the principal is accountable to the overall school operations (Bennaars, et al., 1994; Murphey, 1995; Sergiovanni, 2001). Moreover, according to MoE (2002) there are main activities and responsibilities of principals, which are instructional, as well as leadership and management aspects are identified.

2.6.1 ADMINISTRATIVE LEADERSHIP

The major role of the school principals is providing the materials needed by the group he/she is leading. According to Alessandro, Castro, Ray and Vereline (2004) the basis of good leadership is honorable character and selfless service to organization. So principals have to manage daily operations and environment through efficiency and effectively aligning resources with vision and goals. Valuable resources include financial, human, time, materials, technology, physical plant, and other system components. Moe (2003).The general aim of educational administration is to ensure that the school system functions properly ,that is according to preconceived purposes and plans of action (Liamage,2006).There for administrators need to identify and approve resources and time lines required for learning activities in accordance organizational requirement. There for principals allocate resources and manage school operations in order to ensure a save and productive learning environment and mobilize, allocate and utilize resources, including technology, to support student and staff learning. Principals understand, uphold and model professional ethics, policies and promote the values and challenges of the divers' school community and report to the community and stalk holders on effective and efficient use and

management of school resources. (MOE, 2003). Thus the school principals as administrators connect the school with the community and have to involve parents and communities In improving student learning and provide parents and students with relevant information about available school services (instructional behavioral and psychological) to address student learning needs .As Recharad Elmore. (2000) puts it :the job of administrative leaders is primarily about enhancing the skills and knowledge of the people of the people in the organization ,crating common culture of expectations around the use of those skills and knowledge, holding the various pieces of the organization together in a productive relationship with each other , and holding individuals accountable for their responsibilities.

2.6.2 PRINCIPAL AS INSTRUCTIONAL LEADER

Instructional leadership is a fundamental to successful school leadership. Instructional leadership role is the premeditated process to improve the quality of teaching and learning in schools. Therefore, the roles of principals as instructional leaders are to provide guidance to teachers on curriculum and pedagogy, encourage students to analyze weaknesses and guide teachers and students. In addition, instructional leaders should work with the limitations of existing school resources and improve the quality of teaching.

The role of a principal as an instructional leader receives support from many researchers. For example: Hallinger (2003) suggest that instructional leadership of a principal has to do with effective communication with, and the motivation, supervision, and development of staff, dealing with pupils, and the solving of problems and the resolving of conflicts among staff and pupils. In today's world, Hanny (1987:209), perceives, effective principals are expected to be effective instructional leaders. The principal must be knowledgeable about curriculum development, supervision, staff development, and teachers' evaluation.

2.6.2.1 CURRICULUM DEVELOPMENT

Curriculum development is the base for education on which the teaching learning process is planned and implemented (Adesina, 1990). Curriculum development is the reviewing of educational curriculum at regular time intervals to improve and develop it. It is related to

teaching and learning process which involve look back to what teachers have been taught teaching, what students are learning, how it is organized and with what success.

The principal is the leader of the school and should possess leadership activities, in addition, to understand thoroughly the curriculum. The principal must set and accept relevant role expectation in determining objectives of instruction. Principals must also lead the way in developing in students a positive attitude about learning since the quality attitudes help pupils to become increasingly proficient in attaining knowledge and skills ends (Maslow, 1999). Therefore, it is the responsibility of the principal to provide the leadership undertaking of the activities for the school effectiveness and for teaching and learning process.

2.6.2.2 GOAL CLARIFICATION

Well-understood and well-advertised goals for schools and classrooms are essential. Schools aspire to high performance result from the nature of the goals that are established and the nature of the goal setting process Ubben and Hughes (1997). Meaningful learning is more likely to take place when the learner and teacher have general idea of the goal being pursued. No matter how much is done in the school, it is meaningless unless teachers and students know why they are doing and where they are going. Hence, principals are expected to make clear the general and specific objectives of the instructional process in order for the teachers and students accept and follow any educational program if they get its value, and importance (Gamage, 2006).

2.6.2.3 STAFF DEVELOPMENT

Staff development is a continuous professional development in order to promote teachers profession expertise through involving in problem solving activities (Dimmock, 1993). Promoting teachers professional development, according to Sheppard (1996) is the most influential instructional leadership behavior at both the elementary and high school levels. Among the role of an instructional leader is promoting school wide professional development.

If the intention of the principal is to get school improvement programs implemented and if his/her target is to provide quality education for all students, one of the major and most important concerns should be promoting school-wide continuous professional development (CPD). Hence,

a school principal as an instructional leader needs to motivate all individuals who are eligible to take part in CPD program and work with them.

According to the Ethiopian Ministry of Education (MoE, 2009), the aim of CPD is to improve teachers performance in the classroom in order to raise student achievement and learning because, directly or indirectly, there is a link between students result and teachers performance. CPD is a career long process of improving knowledge, skills, and attitudes centered on the local context and particularly classroom practices. Therefore, attracting, retaining, and developing teachers across the professional life cycle have become policy priorities in many countries (OECD, 2005)

2.6.2.4 SUPERVISION

Supervision is a provisional service and a core function of educational leaders. It plays a key role in the improvement of learning through the monitoring and improvement of instruction. Principals have responsibility to help teachers improve their practice and to hold them accountable for meeting their commitments to teaching and learning. The school principal works with the classroom teachers, students and supervisors in the selection of appropriate curricular or school activities, choice of subjects, textbooks, work scheduling, use of teaching aids and facilities teaching methods and methods of evaluating school and student progress. When principals carried out supervision activity in a well-arranged manner, it promotes teacher development (Sergiovanni, 2001). Hence, making effective Supervision at a school level is crucial to improve the teaching learning process at the spot. Whatever attempt made at the various levels it is meaningless unless supervisory roles are strengthened at the school level.

2.6.2.5 EVALUATION

There are many definitions offered to the concept of evaluation in education. For example, Aspinwal et al (1992) defines it as part of decision-making process. According to Manahan and Hengest, (1982) evaluation is the process of ascertaining or judging the value or amount of something by use of standard of appraisal. An important role a principal should play in a school setting is evaluating the result of teaching. The principal should arrange for all period of self-evaluation of the school program through commonly accepted survey guides, standardized test

results, and action research projects. Evaluation of teaching result helps to measure students 'ability and it is used to diagnose students 'weaknesses. Finally, evaluation helps to measure the school activities whether the school is meeting the developmental and educational needs of the children. Evaluation is also used to assess whether instructional goals have been achieved or not.

Indeed, successful implementation of instructional program depends largely on the individual leadership of the school and commitment of teaching staff. Hence motivating teachers for the improvement of teaching and learning is what is expected from the principal during the process of evaluation. So, whether the skill, knowledge and other services to students are delivered well or not must be regularly reviewed and improved. In this view, the best evaluation is that which has a positive effect on instructional improvement (Leggette, 1981).

From the points raised above, one can understand that the objective of evaluation is to the benefit of teachers by rewarding and promoting for their well deeds and by motivating and encouraging improving their weak side. On the other hand, Monahan and Hengest (1982), have some points to the principal as a leader. That is, the principal is a crucial person to pass decision on important educational issues of the school. Therefore, his/her decision should be well founded.

2.6.2.6 RESEARCH WORK

Research work is in particular the most important one that deserves to be given priority (Moon, et al, 2000). The necessary pre condition must be fulfilled by the school principals for the undertaking of research in the school by teachers. According to Dimmock (2000), school principals should motivate teachers to recognize research to solve school problems and on effective teaching and learning because school effectiveness and improvement will be difficult without research.

In general, principals are expected to mobilize teachers to study and reflect on their practice so that research serves the professionalization of teachers on research.

2.7 CHALLENGES FACED BY SCHOOL PRINCIPALS

In carrying out the task of leadership, principals usually face many challenges. Stressing this point, different scholars listed different challenges that impede leadership responsibility of

principals. Some of these include; lack of skills, lack of resources, lack of vision, will and courage, teachers-principal interaction, the way of decision making and other school related problems.

2.7.1 LACK OF SKILLS

To be influential leader in the school and to address the educational leadership responsibilities, principals need to have skills and training that make them effective and efficient leader. Regarding to this Clatter (1998) states that professional knowledge, skill and attitude have great impact on the achievement of organizational goals and objectives, and the lack of skills will create on impediment to the principals. Mcwan (2003) states that while many institutions restructuring their administration programs to provide more opportunities to develop leadership skills in addition to academic knowledge a gap remains between the academic and real world.

Therefore lack of skill is a common impediment to principals in their educational leadership responsibility.

2.7.2 LACK OF RESOURCE

Resource is one of the very important things for school improvement and long term effectiveness. In research synthesis about practices in high performance schools, the finding that role to resources is evidence Ubben and Hughes (1997), in other worlds a lack of resource (Financial, physical or human) can be a serious obstacle to principal to carry out their task effectively. Principals may want to lead and the situation and expectation of others may call for his /her leadership. But if the resources necessary to implement his/her leadership are inadequate, the principals will face a significant impediment (Gorton, 1983).

2.7.3 LACK OF VISION, WILL AND COURAGE

A vision should a desire future state for the school, which implies that the school should be striving to attain something different from current state. Responsible and accountable school leaders develop clear visions which focus on academic achievements of students. Their activity inspires and leads new and challenging innovations. These leaders also establish clear goals and

keep them in front of attention such leaders expect high performance with achievable goals and objectives through planning and organizing (Leithwood, et al., 2006).

Vision, will, or courage of school leadership is highly related to their effectiveness. Hant in Carlson (1996:140) stated that; visionary leadership consists of “focusing attention on the vision” communicating the vision personally demonstrating trustworthiness, displaying respect and taking risks”. McEwan (2003:14) also strengthen the role of vision as “we are our own worst enemy. But, with vision, will and courage any principal could become effective school leadership”. From the writers idea visionary leadership take out schools failure through focusing at vision and translating into practice.

2.7.4 LACK WORK EXPERIENCE

The ability to learn from experience is one that leader needs to develop and foster. School leaders obviously should work for a few years as a teacher before he/she assumes a leadership so that he/she could gain a number of understandings about students, the role of the community, the problems and teaching, and some of the school administrative problems. Because the leader works with a wide variety of people, it is valuable if his work experience includes some practical experience outside of the field of professional education that he/she could gain through panel discussion, conference, seminar or workshops, in light of this point (Corbally, 1961; Douglas, 1988) pointed out that through such experience, the prospective leader can gain understanding and skills in working with people, if he recognizes the opportunity for learning from experience. In effect the more the experienced leader will become the more effective school leader.

2.7.5 LACK OF TIME

One major difference among principals is how they choose to use the time they do available (McEwan, 2003) Rosser, Vicki J.(cited Roaden, 1970) further stated that in order to enhance the schools performance, principals should focus on major missions of the schools, teaching and

learning, research and community service, unless the principals free themselves from the routine chores of the office, however, and reserve some free time for study and reflection on the purposes and program of the academic body over which they prided, their decisions must inevitably be superficial, uninformed, and often inconsistent.

2.7.6 LACK OF DECISION MAKING ABILITY

The ability to make effective decision is vital to any individual success as a leader and an important component in any organization. According to Musaazi (1982:100), decision making is “a conscious choice from among a well defined set of competing alternatives”. A leader in any organization has to make the right decision at the right time; this shows that in the school system, the ability of effective decision making is useful to the principal in his instructional leadership.

As (MoE 2002) stated in the concept paper of principals the first and foremost for the principal who is working in administrative line is making effective decision. As Gorton (1987:102) explained “To make effective decision one should collaborate with necessary bodies from the upper echelons and on the other hand with subordinates sometimes with students. Some principals are familiar with directive decision making approach by which principals more collecting information.

Others exercise consultative decision making to get the idea of their subordinates even other encourages participative decision making. In this practice the principals share the problem to subordinate and both of them discuss and analyze the issue jointly. This attitude develops mutual trust and generates strong feeling and job satisfaction. To make effective decision, the principals should know not only the alternative but also the type and effectiveness of the decision to be made.

2.8 SUMMARY OF RELATED LITERATURE

The purpose of this chapter is to discuss and provide an analysis on the practice and challenges of school leadership in secondary schools of Bole sub city.

A review of the literature presented a general overview on the practice of school leadership, theory of leadership and concept of school leadership. More relevant to the study, the review of

the literature focused on the role of principals' practicing of different school leadership activities and the challenge faced.

Having implementing the necessary skill of leadership is a characteristic of a good leader. The successes and failures of a school depend on the principals' leadership practice. Effective leaders create conducive environment for teachers to be involved in various issues of school activities.

Active and creative principals work with their staff members in order to create solution to complex problems and provide foundation for school effectiveness. Furthermore, the review of the literature focused on types of leadership style and practicing issues by the principals in a school.

CHAPTER THREE

RESEARCH DESIGN AND METHODOLOGY

INTRODUCTION

The main purpose of this chapter is to provide an overview of the basic research design and methodology that will be used to carry out the study. Under this overview the basic research design, research methodology, source of data, sample population and sampling technique, data collection instruments, procedure of data collection and method of data analyses will be treated in detail.

3.1 DESIGN OF THE STUDY

The intention of the research is to assess the practices and challenges of school leadership in secondary schools of bole sub city. Thus, the researcher used descriptive survey method to reveal the current practice and challenges of principals' in their school leadership. A descriptive survey design is used to undertake this study because the intention of the study is to assess the existing situation and to describe opinions that are held on school leadership practice by participants of the study and to look into school leadership challenges. With regard to the use of descriptive survey research method, Best and Kahn (2003) have argued that this method is concerned with conditions or relationships that exist, opinions that are held, processes that are going on, effects that are evident or trends that are developing.

Thus, the design is preferred on the ground that practices and challenges of school leadership are better perceived from the opinion survey of the school leaders (Principals, vice principals, supervisors) and teaching staff members in schools. Qualitative and quantitative method of data collection (mixed approach) is employed with the assumption that the qualitative data will be gathered through interview while the quantitative data would be collected through document review and survey questionnaire. And amongst the three types of mixed approaches, the QUAN-QUAL model, also known as the triangulation mixed method design, has been preferred since it allows concurrently collecting and equally weighting both qualitative and quantitative data throughout the same study and duration.

The main advantage of this method is that the strengths of the qualitative data (e.g., data about the context) offset the weaknesses of the quantitative data (e.g., ecological validity), and the strengths of the quantitative data (e.g., generalizability) offset the weaknesses of the qualitative data (e.g., context dependence)..

Thus, the method is preferred on the ground that practices and challenges of school leadership are better perceived from the judgment survey of school principals/ vice principals, supervisors and secondary school teachers.

3.2 SOURCES OF DATA

Data were collected using two sources: primary and secondary. The primary sources of the study were key informants from the sub city including supervisors, principals, vice principals and teachers of the five secondary schools. Those in the managerial position were contacted as information sources for the reason that they directly involved in the practices of schools leadership. Teachers were taken as source of information for the reason that they were direct beneficiaries of the service delivered. In addition, information was collected from Secondary sources of the study.

As a secondary source the data collected from documents mainly focused on records and minutes concerning the school based supervision and instructional leadership support in the secondary schools. In addition to this, other relevant documents of the schools were reviewed and these include documents such as brochures that state the vision, mission, goals, and manuals prepared for training purposes.

3.3 SAMPLE POPULATION AND SAMPLING TECHNIQUES

Under Bole Sub City there are eight government secondary schools. The schools were namely Beshalle Secondary and Preparatory school, Bole Medhanealem Preparatory School, Dr. Haddis Secondary School, Lem Secondary School, Ayer Amba Secondary School, Bole Community Secondary School, Bole Bulbula Secondary School & Indod Secondary School.

Among these, using simple random sampling, out of 8 secondary schools five (Beshalle secondary and preparatory school, Lem Secondary School, Bole Bulbula Secondary School, Ayer Amba Secondary School& Dr. Haddis Secondary School) of them are sampled for this

study and for the reason that the characteristics of the schools are the same and this is believed to be fairly representative and manageable and enable to arrive at modest generalization about the whole population. Teachers are randomly selected, but for the principals, vice-principals and supervisors the researcher makes survey the entire population.

To this end, 166 teachers, in the sample secondary schools listed above, have been selected through random sampling, the lottery method in particular, for this technique is provides equal chance of being selected and allows the opportunity to obtain representative sample (Seyoum and Ayalew, 1989). On the other hand, interview was held with all of the 5(100%) principals, 15(100%) vice principals and 5(100%) supervisors.

Table 1: Size of Population and Sample

No	Types of respondent	Target population			Sample population			Sample population in percent(%)			Data gathering instrument
		M	F	T	M	F	T	M	F	T	Questionnaires
1	Teachers	257	75	332	120	46	166	72.3	27.7	100	

3.4 Instruments of Data Collection

The researcher had employed three types of data gathering tools. The data from the primary source was collected through questionnaire and interview while the secondary data were gathered through documentary review.

3.4.1 QUESTIONNAIRE

Questionnaire was put into practice, because it is suitable for collecting factual information, opinion and attitude from large population and it can be easily and quickly analyzed (Wilkinson and Birmingham, 2003). It was utilized as the chief instrument to collect the data.

The questionnaire was made close ended. It enclosed a Likert scale where the respondents could depict their degree of agreement or disagreement at five point scales in line with the significance of issues addressed in the research questions.

The questionnaire was developed based on the basic questions. Following its construction, it was reviewed by the advisor. Then the instruments of data collection were pilot tested at Medhanealem Secondary School prior to putting them in to practice.

The pilot test was conducted to test the validity and reliability of the instruments. The pretest was accomplished with the aim of confirming items included in the instrument could facilitate the researcher to collect the required information. The feedback on the relevance of the questionnaire content implied that the instrument was consistent.

The questionnaire was prepared for teachers. The items of questionnaires were classified under the five basic research questions. The response category laid down was a Likert scale ranging from strongly agree to strongly disagree (5 = strongly agree, 4= agree, 3= undecided, 2= disagree and 1 = strongly disagree).

3.4.2 INTERVIEW

In addition to the questionnaire, the study has employed a semi-structured interview. A semi-structured interview was conducted with the schools principals, vice principals and supervisors. Thus, an interview guide was prepared by the researcher (see AppendixA-2) and conducted in a face to face interaction. The interview guide (a written list of questions) was prepared and conducted in English language. The interviews were conducted in the office of each principals after school time was over (i.e., around 3 to 6 pm) in different days for each of the principals, vice principals and supervisions. In addition to this, the interview took place in ranges of 30 to50 minutes for each of them and the researcher used notebook to take down the information provided by the informants. Finally, interview notes were taken; organized, summarized.

3.4.3 DOCUMENT REVIEW

The researcher has reviewed the rules and regulations of the sample secondary schools. Furthermore, the secondary school curricula, annual reports, inspectional standard level of the sample secondary schools , feed backs provided from the sub-city to these schools and other essential documents were reviewed in order to substantiate the data obtained via questionnaire and interview

3.5 METHOD OF DATA ANALYSIS

In this study, the researcher has used both qualitative and quantitative analyses. The quantitative data were organized and analyzed using SPSS.

Thus, descriptive statistics such as frequency counts, percentage, mean value and standard deviation have been employed for the analysis. Besides, the data gathered through interview and document review were analyzed in the form of descriptive narration. As a result, the researcher has tried to enhance reliability and /or accuracy of the findings through triangulation of information sought from different data sources and via examining the evidences extracted from those primary and secondary data sources.

3.6 ETHICAL CONSIDERATION

Most importantly the researcher conducted the study based on professional as well as the basic principles of research. From professional point of view, the researcher has never disclosed or presented personal identities and related qualities of the respondents of this study.

Ethical issues were grouped into informed consent procedures, dishonesty, confidentiality towards participants or sponsors and protecting the anonymity and privacy of research participants (Sarantakos, 2005). Based on the basic principles, the researcher proposed a set of ethical and moral procedure and informed the participants just before in depth interview and filling out the questionnaire. The participants were informed that information obtained from them remain confidential. Besides they were informed that their names will not be written or exposed on report and will never be used in connection with any of the information they revealed.

CHAPTER FOUR

DATA PRESENTATION, ANALYSIS AND INTERPRETATION

This chapter deals with the presentation, analysis and interpretation of data gathered from sample of data obtained from teachers, principals, vice principals and supervisors. It consists of two parts. The first part is concerned with presenting personal information of the sample population and the second part deals with the presentation and analysis of the findings of the study.

In this study, 166 teachers, 5 principals and 15 vice principals from five secondary schools and 5 supervisors from Bole sub city education office were included. Questionnaires were distributed to all sample teachers and were 166 filled and returned. Interviews with principals, vice principals and sub city supervisors were conducted.

Therefore, analysis was made based on the data obtained from a total of 166 respondents. Thus, the quantitative as well as qualitative analysis of data was incorporated into this chapter. The qualitative part was supposed to be complementary to the quantitative analysis. All the data obtained through questionnaires and interviews based on the basic questions posed in chapter one, interpretation and discussion were carried by taking in to account theories discussed and empirical works reviewed in the literature.

The study covered five secondary schools of Bole sub city namely; Beshalle secondary and preparatory school, Lem secondary school, Bole bulbula secondary school, Ayer Amba secondary school & Dr. Haddis secondary school. A total of 166 questionnaires were prepared and distributed for 166 sample teachers. All of the questionnaires (100%) that were distributed to the teachers were filled and returned to the researcher.

In addition, to supplement the information gathered through questionnaire, interviews were held with five supervisors, five principals and fifteen vice principals. Besides information from document analysis was used to triangulate the data obtained. In analyzing the data of the study, different statistical techniques and procedures were used. Initially, the data collected through questionnaire were coded and inserted into SPSS for analysis.

Then the mean teachers' group respondents were identified and analysis was done using the average mean of the group respondents. To determine the existence/implementation of the

different school leadership practices in the secondary schools of the sub city, an average point of decision was set.

To this end, a test of significance has been carried out with five dimensions of school leadership, five leadership roles of secondary school leaders and major challenges hindering school leadership items. Items involved in the questionnaires were classified into two major categories. The first category dealt with general background information of the respondents, while the second part has treated specific issues of the study.

Hence, this leads to use different approaches in treating or analyzing the data from the two categories questions. Therefore, frequency and percentages were used for the analysis of characteristics of respondents. On the other hand, mean, standard deviation and grand mean was used for the analysis of specific items.

Therefore, in the first part of the analysis, the characteristics of the respondents in relation to their age, sex, education level, qualification and work experience were tabulated and analyzed as indicated under table 2. In the second part of the analysis the views of the teachers' respondents were analyzed and interpretations were made based on mean, grand mean and standard deviation.

4.1. CHARACTERISTICS OF RESPONDENTS

This section provides some basic background information pertaining to sample population that helps to know the overall information of the respondents with the assumption that it might have some kind of relationship shed light on the practice and challenges of school leadership in Bole sub city. Accordingly, the characteristics of the study groups were examined in terms of sex, age, level of education and work experience. The summary of data was presented in table 2 here under.

TABLE 2. DEMOGRAPHIC CHARACTERISTICS OF RESPONDENTS

No	item	Category of item	Respondents									
			Teachers		Principals		Vice principals		Supervisors		Total	
			N	%	N	%	N	%	N	%	N	%
1	sex	Male	120	72.3	5	100	12	80	4	80	141	73.8
		Female	46	27.7	0	0	3	20	1	20	50	26.2
		Total	166	100	5	100	15	100	5	100	191	100
2	Age in years	25-30	53	31.9	0	0	1	6.7	0	0	54	28.3
		31-35	47	28.3	1	20	3	20	1	20	52	27.2
		36-40	30	18.1	1	20	5	33.3	0	0	36	18.8
		41-45	16	9.6	2	40	3	20	0	0	21	11
		46-50	12	7.2	1	20	2	13.3	0	0	15	7.9
		51 & above	8	4.8	0	0	1	6.7	4	80	13	6.8
		Total	166	100	5	100	15	100	5	100	191	100
3	Qualification or level of education	BA/BSC/BED degree	134	80.72	0	0	6	40	2	40	142	74.3
		MA/MSC/MED degree	32	19.3	5	100	9	60	3	60	49	25.7
		Other	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
		Total	166	100	5	100	15	100	5	100	191	100
4	Work experience	1-5	20	12	0	0	0	0	-	-	20	10.5
		6-10 years	52	31.3	0	0	1	6.7	-	-	53	27.7
		11-15 years	48	28.9	1	20	1	6.6	1	20	51	26.7
		16-20 years	20	12	1	20	6	40	-	-	27	14.2
		21-25	8	4.8	2	40	4	26.7	-	-	14	7.3
		26-30	10	6	1	20	3	20	-	-	14	7.3
		31 & above	8	4.8	0	0	0	0	4	80	12	6.3
		Total	166	100	5	100	15	100	5	100	191	100

As shown under item 1 of table 2, 120(72.3%) of teachers are male. Only 46(27.7%) of teachers are females. This implies that the participation of both sex found to be not proportional.

This might be due to the fact that the number of female teachers at secondary school level is generally low. When it comes to the sex of interviews respondents: 5(100%), 12(80%) and 4(80%) of Principals, vice principals and supervisors are male respectively. On the other hand, only 3(20%), and 1(20%) vice principals and supervisors respectively are females. On the other hand the principals of five secondary schools were all male respondents. This shows that the participation of females were almost insignificant even in the front line of leading position and

teaching in secondary schools. This also implies that female teachers do not get a chance to be in leadership positions.

Age distribution of the respondents under item 2, indicates that the majority of the respondents, 130(78.3%) of teachers are found in the ranges of 25-40 age. With reference to the age of the interview respondents; majority of the participants (principals and vice principal) are in the ranges of 25-40 age and 4(80%) of supervisors are above 50 years old which is believed to be at their adult age. This shows that, the majority of respondents were matured enough to know what has been happening in their respective schools, hence will be able to provide pertinent and detailed information about school leadership practice it is there for anticipated that they could be in a better position to help the school community in creating strong leadership from the top to lower level.

With regard to work experience, the teacher respondents were asked their experience in their teaching position and the majority of them, 120(72.2%) had a teaching experience of 6-20 years, 20(12%) had 1-5 years and the rest had more than 20 years of experience..

With regard to educational level, 134(80.72%) teachers have Bachelor of Education degrees. While only 32(19.3%) of teachers respondents have master's degree. This indicates that most teachers are not in possession of the required teaching qualifications. Most teachers have first degree while few numbers of teachers were master's degree. But from those 134 teachers who have first degree some were pursuing their education in summer program training. This scenario should be encouraged for the concerned body since most teachers are not well qualified to perform their duties effectively.

As regards individual interview respondents; 5(100%), 9(60%), 3(60%) of principals, vice principals and supervisors were second degree holders respectively. However for a principals, criteria according to Blue Print of teachers development program (MOE, 2007, pp-30-31) stated that the academic qualification required for secondary school principal is a master's degree. Therefore 2(40%) and 2(40%) of vice principals and supervisors need to upgrade their education level.

4.2 Interpretation of Data

The questionnaires have close and open-ended items. Each item of the closed ended part of questionnaire prepared for school staffs was designed in a form of five-point rating scale comprising: SA, A, UD, DA and SD. These responses are given values 5, 4, 3, 2, and 1, respectively. Scores of 5 and 4 indicate the practice or activity of the approach is at a very high level of school leadership. Scores 1 and 2 indicate the practice or activity of the approach is strong and prominent. A score 3 indicates the practice or activity of the approach is at a medium level of school leadership practices and challenges.

TABLE 3: RESPONSES ON PRINCIPALS' EFFORT ON PLANNING ACTIVITIES

No	Item	Responses					Total	Mean	SD	
			SA	A	UD	DA				SDA
1	The leader develops clear, specific and participatory long term and short term educational plans of the school according to the national and regional educational goals and strategies.	N	27	75	48	12	4	166	3.66	.919
		%	16.3	45.2	28.9	7.2	2.4			
2	The leader ensure that instructional plans and practices are effective and meet the needs of all students	N	15	77	62	12		166	3.57	.757
		%	9.0	46.4	37.3	7.2				
3	The leader facilitate stake holders' participation in planning	N	26	70	44	14	6	160	3.60	.985
		%	15.7	42.2	26.5	8.4	3.6			
4	The leader allocate sufficient budget for implementation of the educational plans	N	20	56	72	10	8	166	3.42	.949
		%	12.0	33.7	43.4	6.0	4.8			
5	The leader monitoring the status of annual plan	N	30	76	38	16	4	166	3.68	.964
		%	18.1	45.8	22.9	9.6	2.4			
6	The leader having regular staff meeting to discuss about the plan	N	29	72	41	18	4	166	3.63	.978
		%	17.5	43.4	24.7	10.8	2.4			
Grand mean								3.59	0.925	

Like any organization, schools need an institutional plan to realize effectiveness in their institution. Educators in the field have given a number of definitions for the conduct of planning in schools. Ubben and Huges (1997) explain that planning in the schools as a process that involves the translation of concepts, ideas, beliefs into operational process and measure out comes. Success of institutional planning depends on the dynamism and interest of the head. Regarding item one of table 3, the respondents were whether the leaders have developed clear, specific and participatory long term and short term educational plans of the school according to the national and regional educational goals and strategies or not. The majority of teachers 27(16.3%), 75(45.2%) and 48(28.9) responded to be strongly agree, agree and undecided respectively. Whereas, 12(7.2%) and 4(2.4%) of teachers responded disagree and strongly disagree. This implies that the principals have developed clear, specific and participatory long term and short term educational plans of the school according to the national and regional educational goals and strategies moderately.

Concerning the leader ensure that instructional plans and practices are effective and meet the needs of all students. 77(46.4%) and 62(37.3%) of teachers responded to agree and undecided respectively on the issue. Whereas 15(9%) of teachers rated to strongly agree. But no teachers rated to strongly disagree. This means that some of the respondents had satisfaction to the leader ensure that instructional plans and practices are effective and meet the needs of all students. But some of the teachers were undecided on the issue.

According to item three of table 3, 15(9%), 70(42.2%), 44(26.5%), 14(8.4%) and 6(3.6%) of teachers responded to strongly agree, agree, undecided, disagree and strongly disagree respectively. From this one can understands that the leader facilitate stake holders' participation in planning were moderate as there are 70(42.2%) of teachers who were undecided on the issue.

As shown in item four of similar table regarding the leader allocate sufficient budget for implementation of the educational plans. 20(12%) and 56(33.7%) of teachers responded strongly agree and agree. Whereas, 72(43.4%), 10(6%) and 8(4.8%) of teachers responded undecided, disagree and strongly disagree. This implies that allocation of sufficient budget for implementations of the educational plans by leader were moderate.

The respondents were also asked on item five of similar table whether the leader monitors the status of annual plan or not. The majority of respondents 30(18.1%) and 76 (45.8) of teachers

responded to be strongly agree and agree. On the other hand 38(22.9%), 16(9.6%) and 4(2.4%) of teachers, responded undecided, disagree and strongly disagree. This shows that the leader monitoring the status of annual plan very well.

Item six of the same table inquires whether or not the leader holds regular staff meeting to discuss the plan. The majority of respondents 29(17.5%) and 72(43.4%) of teachers responded to strongly agree and agree. But 41(24.7%), 18(10.8%) and 4(2.4) teachers responded undecided, disagree and strongly disagree. From the above data one can understand that most of the time the leader convenes regular staff meeting to discuss the plan.

In addition finding from interviews shows that there is strategic and one year plan in all five secondary schools.

One of the principals of secondary school said that

Planning is a major and most important activity of ours (to mean principals and vice principals). Our school has three years strategic plan and one year cascaded plan. In both three years planning and one year planning concerned bodies (parents, communities, teachers, students, supervisors and support staff of the school) participated on planning all activities done in the future.

On the other hand one of the vice principals' secondary school explained that:

We prepared strategic plan of the school in collaboration with external supervisor and school community (teachers, principal, vice principals, representative of students and supportive staff of the school) without the participation of parents and community. Because Bulbula secondary school established and started it's activity in this year.

The result of document analysis also indicated that there were no specified documents showing the participation of parents and community done before preparing strategic planning in Bulbula secondary school. But in the other four schools the participation of parents and community were very high. In this regard, literature revealed that school plan must be democratically oriented and should involve everyone concerned: teachers, students, parents, and community and effective plans are those that require participation of all stakeholders (Coombs as cited in Tigistu, 2012)

TABLE 4: RESPONSES ON PRINCIPALS' EFFORT ON GOAL SETTING.

No	Item	Responses					Total	Mean	SD	
			SA	A	UD	DA				SD
1	The leader capable of developing future school vision , goal, mission and objectives clearly	N	33	61	50	18	4	166	3.61	1.002
		%	19.9	36.7	30.1	10.8	2.4	100		
2	The leader capable of making clear the school goals and objectives to teachers and students	N	29	71	50	16		166	3.68	.874
		%	17.5	42.8	30.1	9.6		100		
3	The leader capable of setting directions and encouraging the staff towards achieving the expected goals	N	30	66	40	26	4	166	3.55	1.036
		%	18.1	39.8	24.1	15.7	2.4	100		
4	The leader motivates teachers for the best Performance.	N	25	53	52	26	8	166	3.37	1.075
		%	15.1	31.9	31.3	15.7	4.8	100		
5	The leader encourage students to effective performance	N	18	56	64	28		166	3.39	.892
		%	10.8	33.7	38.6	16.9		100		
6	The leader works to improve students' disciplinary problems.	N	32	48	62	20	2	166	3.54	.981
		%	19.3	28.9	37.3	12.0	1.2	100		
Grand mean									3.523	0.977

School leaders are required to develop future school vision, goal, mission and objectives clearly. Making future school vision, goal, mission and objectives clearly is the most important strategy for a better performance of the intended plan. Consequently, the research showed in table four item one 33(19.1%) and 61(36.7%) almost 57% of teachers responded strongly agree and agree respectively. On the other hand 50(30.1%), 18(10.8%) and 4(2.4%) of teachers responded undecided, disagree and strongly disagree. This implies that most of school leaders are capable of developing future school vision, goal, and mission and objectives moderately.

Regarding whether the leader is capable of making clear the school goals and objectives to teachers and students the majorities of respondents 29(17.5%) and 71(42.8%) of teachers responded strongly agree and agree respectively but 50(30.1%) and only 16(9.6%) of teachers responded undecided and disagree. This shows that most of school leaders of five secondary schools are capable of making clear the school goals and objectives to teachers and students.

The other fundamental issue regarding school leaders whether the leader is capable of setting directions and encourages the staff towards achieving the expected goals. On the study it is shown that 30(18.1%) and 66(39.6%) almost 58% of teachers responded strongly agree and agree respectively. But 26(15.7%) and 4(2.4%) of teachers responded disagree and strongly disagree respectively. 40(24.1%) of teachers responded undecided. From the above data the majority of respondents responded on the leader capable of setting directions and encouraging the staff towards achieving the expected goals to be moderate.

Concerning item 4, the respondents were asked whether the leader motivates teachers for the best Performance or not. Some of respondents 25(15.1%) and 53(31.9%) of teachers responded strongly agree and agree respectively. On the other hand 26(15.7%) and 8(4.8%) of teachers, responded to disagree and strongly disagree respectively. 52(31.3%) of teachers, were undecided on the issue. This implies that some of the school leaders motivate teachers for the best performance but 20.5% of the teachers responded that the school leaders do not motivate teachers.

Item five of the table inquires whether the leaders encourage students to effective performance or not. Some of the respondents 18(10.8%) and 56(33.7%) of the teachers responded strongly agree and agree respectively. And 64(38.6%) of the respondents were not decided on the issue. But only 28(16.9%) disagree on issue and there is no strongly disagreed respondents. This shows that some leaders encourage the student to effective performance but others do not.

The last item of the table asks whether the leader work to improve students' disciplinary problems or not. Accordingly, 32(19.3%) and 48(28.9%) of teachers responds strongly agree and agree respectively. but 20(12%) and 2(1.2%) teachers responded disagree and strongly disagree respectively. On the other hand 62(37.3%) of teachers responded undecided on item.

This implies that some of the leaders work to improve the students disciplinary problems but others do not work on it.

TABLE 5: RESPONSES ON PRINCIPALS' EFFORT ON DECISION MAKING ABILITY

No	Item	Responses					Total	Mean	SD	
			SA	A	UD	DA				SD
1	The leader ability to prioritize problems and evaluate various alternatives	N	16	54	72	18	4	166	3.37	.893
		%	9.6	32.5	43.4	10.8	2.4	100		
2	The leader using participatory decision making process	N	14	57	57	30	6	166	3.26	.977
		%	8.4	34.3	34.3	18.1	3.6	100		
3	The leader evaluate activities of the teachers' and making fair judgments	N	20	60	52	32	2	166	3.39	.970
		%	12.0	36.1	31.3	19.3	1.2	100		
4	The leader promoting mutual respect and create an atmosphere of trust among followers.	N	11	67	48	32	4	166	3.30	.946
		%	6.6	40.4	28.9	19.3	2.4	100		
5	The leader be able to confront challenges and school problems courageously	N	21	49	72	20	4	166	3.38	.938
		%	12.7	29.5	43.4	12.0	2.4	100		
6	The school community is satisfied with decision made in the school	N	14	48	58	28	12	166	3.15	1.053
		%	8.4	28.9	34.9	16.9	7.2	100		
Grand mean									3.308	0.962

Decision making can be one of leader's roles in the school. In every organization system and also in the school system fulfilling the needs of everyone might be difficult. According to the research made 16(9.6%) and 54(32.5%) of teachers responded to strongly agree and agree respectively. 30(18.1%) and 6(3.6%) of teachers responded disagree and strongly disagree respectively. Whereas, 72(43.4%) of teachers responded to undecided. Thus, the research showed that the respondents most frequently responded to agreed on the leader ability to prioritize problems and evaluate various alternatives.

One of the activities of leaders is to adopt participatory decision making process in the school. And Participation of teachers is inevitable since they are playing the major leadership role in the

school premises. According to the respondents 14(8.4%) and 57(34.3%) of teachers responded to strongly agree and agree respectively. Whereas, 30(18.1%) and 6(3.6%) of teachers responded disagree and strongly disagree. And 57(34.3%) of teachers responded undecided. This shows that most of the school leaders use participatory decision making in the school.

Item 3 of table 5 inquires whether the leader evaluate activities of the teachers' and making fair judgments or not 20(12%) and 60(36.1) of teacher responded to strongly agree and agree respectively. and 52(31.3%), 32(19.3%) and 2(1.2%) undecided, disagree and strongly disagree respectively. the data collected depicted that some of school principals make fair judgment openly but the others not.

Item 4 of table 5 asks whether the leader promoting mutual respect and create an atmosphere of trust among followers. 11(6.6%) and 67(40.4%) strongly agree and agree respectively. But 32(19.3%) and 2(1.2%) of respondents responded disagree and strongly disagree and 48(28.9%) teachers responded undecided on issue. As the most frequent value confirmed most of the respondents responded that the leader promoting mutual respect and create an atmosphere of trust among followers moderately.

In line with the leader be able to confront challenges and school problems courageously the fifth item in table five 21(12.7%) and 49(29.5%) of respondents responded strongly agree and agree respectively. But 20(12%) and 4(2.4%) respondents responded that disagree and strongly disagree respectively. On the other hand 72(43.4%) respondents undecided on the issue. this implies that most of the teachers did not agree on leader's ability confront challenges and school problems.

Item six enquires whether the school community is satisfied with decision made in the school or not 14(8.4%) and 48(28.9%) responded that strongly agree and agree respectively. In the other hand 28(16.9%) and 12(7.2%) of teachers responded disagree and strongly disagree some of school community dissatisfied with the decision made in school.

TABLE 6: RESPONSES ON PRINCIPALS' EFFORT ON INSTRUCTIONAL LEADERSHIP ROLE

No	Item	Responses						Total	Mean	SD
			SA	A	UD	DA	SD			
1	The leader continuously assist and give constructive feedbacks that improves teachers performance in teaching	N	28	54	52	24	6	166	3.45	1.053
		%	16.9	32.5	31.3	14.5	3.6	100		
2	The leader create facilitative conditions for curriculum implementation	N	24	52	50	30	8	166	3.33	1.086
		%	14.5	31.3	30.1	18.1	4.8	100		
3	The leader motivate teachers to appropriately implement the school curriculum	N	21	49	58	26	12	166	3.25	1.092
		%	12.7	29.5	34.9	15.7	7.2	100		
4	The leader works to make school community members more active participate in problem solving and academic activities.	N	14	64	56	32		166	3.36	.889
		%	8.4	38.6	33.7	19.3		100		
5	The leader capable of evaluating, making fair judgments and ability of planning	N	20	44	60	36	4	166	3.24	1.010
		%	12.0	26.5	36.1	21.7	2.4	100		
6	The leader give more of his time to follow whether the educational activities are carried out in accordance with the plan or not	N	14	56	68	22	6	166	3.30	.931
		%	8.4	33.7	41.0	13.3	3.6	100		
Grand mean									3.321	1.010

As indicated in table -6 item 1 portrays that the leader continuously assist and give constructive feedbacks that improves teachers performance in teaching. Accordingly, teachers replied 28(16.9%) and 54(32.5%) strongly agree and agree respectively. But 24(14.5%) and 6(3.6%) of teachers disagree and strongly disagree on the issue. As well as 52(31.3%) of teachers undecided

on the issue raised. This implies that most of the time school leaders do not give feedback for teachers to improve their performance in teaching.

Item 2 reveals whether the leader create facilitative conditions for curriculum implementation or not. Hence teachers responded strongly agree and agree 24(14%) and 52(31.3%) respectively .but 30(18.1%) and 8(4.8%) of teachers responded that disagree and strongly disagree on the issue. From this analysis there is leaders are not effectively crate facilitative condition for curriculum implementation.

With regard to table 6, the frequency and the percent for response of teachers in item 3 to know the degree of leader's motivation teachers to appropriately implement the school curriculum 21(12.7%) and 49(29.5%) of teachers responded that strongly agree and agree respectively. But 26(15.7%) and 12(7.2%) of teachers disagree and strongly disagree on the issue. And also few number of the teachers undecided whether the leaders motivate teachers to appropriately implement the school curriculum or not. This shows that there is a gap or less focus on leader's motivations of teachers to appropriately implement the school curriculum.

Based on the responses of teachers, item 4, whether the leader works to make school community members more active participate in problem solving and academic activities or not 14(8.4%) and 64(38.6%) of teacher respondents respectively responded that their school leaders involves school community in solving school problems and participating on academic activity. Whereas 32(19.3%) of teachers respondents responded that school leaders do not involved school community in problem solving and academic activities. The remaining of teachers 56(33.7%) undecided on the issue raised. This shows that most of the respondents agree on the participation of school community in problem solving academic activities.

Item 5 enquires whether, the leader is capable of evaluating, making fair judgments and ability of planning 20(12%) and 44(26.5%) of teachers responded strongly agree and agree respectively. On the other hand 36(21.7%) and 4(2.4%) of teachers responded strongly disagree and disagree respectively. This implies that some of the school leaders are capable of evaluating, making fair judgment but others do not.

The last item of the table asks, the leader give more of his time to follow whether the educational activities are carried out in accordance with the plan or not 14(8.4%) and 56(33.7%) of teachers responded strongly agree and agree respectively. But 22(13.3%) and 6(3.6%) of teachers

responded disagree and strongly disagree. And also 68(41%) of the teachers were undecided on issue raised.

As we have seen from the above analysis most of teachers agree on issue of whether the educational activities are carried out in accordance with the plan or not.

Vice principal who participated in interview said that the success of a school is attributed to principal's popularity or reputation. One of the vice principal said,

“To me the principals' role is important to implement curriculum and student achievement. Without his coordination, support and facilitation things will not go smoothly. The way he led his school determines the success of his school. He is a driving force.”

Similarly one of the supervisors stated:

“Yes, at the back of all his success or failure, there is the issue of how well he governed his school community. Though the principals' leadership and make school community members more active participate in problem solving and academic activities. has also significant contribution to student achievement.”

TABLE 7: RESPONSE ON ASSUMED CHALLENGES OF THE SCHOOL LEADERS FACED IN THE SCHOOL

No	Item	Responses					Total	Mean	SD	
			SA	A	UD	DA				SD
1	Lack of training in school leadership.	N	31	37	58	22	14	166	3.30	1.180
		%	18.7	22.3	34.9	13.3	8.4	100		
2	Lack of adequate resource	N	42	36	41	32	13	166	3.38	1.274
		%	25.3	21.7	24.7	19.3	7.8	100		
3	Lack skills and knowledge of promoting and communicating the strategic vision and aims to teachers, students and the community	N	16	46	61	26	13	166	3.16	1.069
		%	9.6	27.7	36.7	15.7	7.8	100		
4	Work over load	N	22	42	56	38	4	166	3.25	1.040
		%	13.3	25.3	33.7	22.9	2.4	100		
5	The problem of selection and placement of school leadership	N	31	56	47	22	8	166	3.49	1.094
		%	18.7	33.7	28.3	13.3	4.8	100		
6	Lack of ability to give professional assistance and guidance to teachers to enable them realize instructional objectives	N	30	48	55	20	13	166	3.37	1.146
		%	18.1	28.9	33.1	12.0	7.8	100		
7	Lack of sharing the problems of school leadership by Higher officials	N	26	47	57	30	6	166	3.34	1.060
		%	15.7	28.3	34.3	18.1	3.6	100		
8	Problem of Working with parents and the community	N	28	37	52	44	4	166	3.25	1.101
		%	16.9	22.3	31.3	26.5	2.4	100		
Grand mean									3.317	1.120

As shown in table 7, item 1 forwarded whether or not there is lack of training in school leadership management or not. In this regard among the respondents 31(18.7%) of teachers and strongly agreed, 37(22.3%) of teachers agreed for the lack of training in school leadership management however 22(13.3%) and 14(8.4%) of teachers disagreed and strongly disagree

respectively as well as some number of teachers unable to decided whether item 1 were a lack training in school leadership or not with mean value 58 (34.9%). This shows that there is lack of training for school leaderships.

In the same table, item 2 describes whether or not there is lack of adequate resource or not. In regarding to this 42(25.3%) and 36(21.7%) of teachers strongly agreed and agree respectively. 32(12.3%) and 13(7.8%)of teachers disagreed and strongly disagree respectively. some number of teachers unable to decided whether item 2 were a lack adequate resources or not with mean value 41(24.7%). From the above analysis there is lack of adequate resources.

On the responses that lack skills and knowledge of promoting and communicating the strategic vision and aims to teachers, students and the community 16(9.6%) and 46(27.7%) strongly agree and agree respectively. however few number of teachers disagreed with frequency number 39. This means there is lack of skill and knowledge of promoting and communicating the strategic vision and aims to teachers, students and community.

Item-4 in the same table, describes whether there is work over load or not on the school leaders , concerning this 22(13.3%) and 42(25.3%) of teachers strongly agree and agree respectively. But 38(22.9%) and 4(2.4%) of teachers disagree and strongly disagree respectively. This means there is work load on school leadership.

Item-5, in the same table describes there is the problem of selection and placement of school leadership. According to respondents about 31(18.7%) and 56(33.7%) of teachers (strongly agreed and agreed) respectively. and 30(18.1%) of teachers also disagreed plus strongly disagreed, however 47(28.3) of teachers unable to decided whether the problem of selection and placement of school leadership or not. This shows that there is the problem of selection and placement of school leadership.

Item-6, in the same table describes lack of ability to give professional assistance and guidance to teachers to enable them realizes instructional objectives. As regards to this 30 (18.1%) and 48(28.9%) of teachers strongly agree and agree respectively. But 20(12%) and 13(7.8%) of teachers disagreed and strongly disagreed on the idea raise in this item. This shows most of teachers strongly agree and agree on the lack of ability to give professional assistance and guidance to teachers to enable them realizes instructional objectives

Item-7, in the same table states concerning about lack of sharing the problems of school leadership by Higher officials the data collected from the respondent indicated that 26(15.7%) and 47(28.3%) of teachers (agreed and strongly agreed) respectively. as well as 30(18.1%) and 6(3.6%) of teachers also (disagreed plus strongly disagreed) respectively. however few percent of respondents undecided on the issue. This shows that most of the time there is lack of sharing the problems of school leaders by higher officials.

Item- 8 , in the same table was the one and the most challenging factor for the school principals, this item revealed that problem of working with parents and the community was hide their effectiveness to lead the school. In this regard 28(16.9%) and 37(22.3%) of teachers strongly agreed plus agreed respectively on the issue that raised in item-8. But 44(26.5%) and 4(2.4%) of teachers disagreed and strongly disagree on the idea that challenges was faced in their day to day tasks, however few percent of teachers undecided on the issue with 31.3%. from the data the researcher has got above most of school leaders are not working with parents and community.

Also, when the researcher conducted interview with principals and vice principals most of them indicated that there had been no in-service training programmers on different issues of leadership. One of school vice principal put it in the following way:

We were not provided any in-service training on different activities of school leadership. What I know about leadership is by asking others leaders and by goggling from internet in the school. And also I have not attended training on formulating strategic vision of the school since I was assigned as school vice principal.

Another reason for the challenges they faced was the lack of sharing the problems of school leadership by higher officials. This was articulated by one of the school leaders as follows:

There was no continuous supervision and monitoring from the sub city education authority concerning teaching leaning process some time supervisors and inspectors come in three or four months and they give some information how to improve the school . Other top level leaders almost they have no role in sharing the problems of school leaders.

CHAPTER FIVE

SUMMARY, CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

The aim of the study was to assess the practice and challenges of school leadership in government schools of Bole sub city. In this chapter, a descriptive method of analysis was used. To achieve the purpose of this study the following basic questions were designed.

1. What are the practices of educational leadership in secondary schools of Bole sub city?
2. What are the challenges that secondary school leaders in Bole sub city encountered in their leadership activities?
3. What are the possible solutions that alleviate the main challenges school leaders' face?

The study was conducted in 5 secondary schools in Bole sub city using 5 principals, 15 vice principals, 166 teachers and 5 supervisors, a total of 191 respondents. Data was collected by questionnaires, interviews and document analysis. Closed ended questions were prepared for teachers and open ended questions as interview were prepared for principals, vice principals and supervisors to obtain necessary data for analysis and the data gathered were analyzed using frequency of the response, percentage, and mean value, grand mean and standard deviation.

The major finding is summarized as follow

5.1 SUMMARY

5.1.1 CHARACTERISTIC OF RESPONDENTS

The result found out that the secondary schools, 120 (72.3 %) of teachers' and all of principals were males hence none number of principals are females. And 12(80%) and 4(80%) of vice principals and supervisors respectively were all male it was implying that the number of female teachers, vice principals and supervisors holding leader ship position and the work environment was male dominated.

It was identified that majority of teachers age range from 25-30 years in the young age which needs to more assistance and support from school leaders and community.

Education level identified 130(78%) of teachers had first degree holders .It implies that high amount of teachers does not fit preparatory class few over all vice principals did not fit the qualification level. ’

With regard to the work experiences of the respondents, 52(31.3%) of teachers had teaching experience for about 6 to 10 years. this indicated that majority of teachers had low experience they need proper support from more experienced teachers.

On the other hand 4 (80%) of supervisors respondents had above 31 years experience and this shows that they provide further support for the leaders and school community.

5.1.2 RESPONSES ON PRINCIPALS' EFFORT ON PLANNING ACTIVITIES

Concerning responses on principals' Effort on planning activities the leader develops clear, specific and participatory long term and short term educational plans of the school according to the national and regional educational goals and strategies. From the analyzed data School principals have developed clear, specific and participatory long term and short term educational plans of the school according to the national and city educational goals and strategies. And also the leaders ensure that instructional plans and practices are effective and meet the needs of all students, most of the teachers agree with this idea but some of the teacher’s undecided on the issue.

5.1.3 RESPONSES ON PRINCIPALS' EFFORT ON GOAL SETTING

The finding of the study indicates that the leader is capable of developing future school vision , goal, mission and objectives clearly, making clear the school goals and objectives to teachers and students, setting directions and encouraging the staff towards achieving the expected goals, motivates teachers for the best Performance and encourage students to effective performance some of respondents agree on issue but half of the respondents undecided on the issue. This shows that there is gap on the principal’s effort on goal setting.

5.1.4 RESPONSES ON PRINCIPALS' EFFORT ON DECISION MAKING ABILITY

Decision making is a conscious human process involving both individual and social phenomenon based upon factual and value premises which concludes with a choice of one behavioral activity from among one or more alternatives with the intention of moving toward some desired state of affairs.

From the data obtained the respondents believed that concerning the leader ability to prioritize problems and evaluate various alternatives, using participatory decision making process, evaluate activities of the teachers' and making fair judgments, Promoting mutual respect and create an atmosphere of trust among followers, able to confront challenges and school problems courageously and the school community is satisfied with decision made in the school most of respondents agree on the ability of decision making of school leaders but some of respondents undecided on the issue.

5.1.5 RESPONSES ON PRINCIPALS' EFFORT ON INSTRUCTIONAL LEADERSHIP ROLE

With regard to the leader's ability to continuously assist and give constructive feedbacks that improves teachers performance in teaching, create facilitative conditions for curriculum implementation, motivate teachers to appropriately implement the school curriculum, works to make school community members more active participate in problem solving and academic activities, capable of evaluating, making fair judgments and ability of planning and give more of his time to follow whether the educational activities are carried out in accordance with the plan or not most of the respondents agree on the school leaders assisting and giving instructional activity in the schools but some of the respondents undecided on the issue.

5.1.6 RESPONSE ON ASSUMED CHALLENGES OF THE SCHOOL LEADERS FACED IN THE SCHOOL

Regarding to school leaders facing challenges in a school during practicing school leadership activities most of the respondents were agreed that the school leaders face some challenges in a school such as lack of training in school leadership, lack of adequate resource ,lack skills and knowledge of promoting and communicating the strategic vision and aims to teachers, students

and the community, work over load, the problem of selection and placement of school leadership, lack of ability to give professional assistance and guidance to teachers to enable them realize instructional objectives, lack of sharing the problems of school leadership by higher officials and problem of working with parents and the community. But some of choose undecided on the issue.

5.2 CONCLUSIONS

Effective school leaders have very strong and clear vision and set of values for their school. They lead their school effectively, contribute smooth leadership practice, and make teachers and other stake holders involve collaboratively in decision making for the success of the school activity. In addition they take part in improving their way of leading their schools having professional skills to overcome the challenges that their schools face. Finally, they evaluate and monitor their plan for the improvements of students' achievements. To sum up, the above points are expected from an effective leadership of the school.

Therefore, data and ideas were gathered from questionnaire, interviews, document analysis and review of the literature; the quantitative portion of the study and the qualitative portion of the study were analyzed to develop reasonable Conclusions about the finding. As such triangulation of the data from these four sources produced the following conclusions.

The qualification of teachers, school vice principals and supervisors related professional skill and knowledge was the intended plan of Ethiopian Ministry Education. It is against what was stipulated in the Blue Print that claim, "secondary school teachers and principals need to have second degree" whereas majority of teachers and few of vice principals and supervisors have first degree. Here lack of qualified teachers and few school leaders was still found to greatly influence performances of schools in general and effectiveness of teachers and school leaders. Therefore it is to conclude that effectiveness of teachers and school leaders influenced by miss match between educational level that were rated to be below the standard set by Ethiopian Ministry of Education.

Planning is a process which involves anticipation of future course of events and deciding the best course of action. It is a process of thinking before doing. To plan is to produce a scheme for future action; to bring about specified results, at specified cost, in a specified period of time. It is

deliberate attempt to influence, exploit, bring about, and control the nature, direction, extent, speed and effects of change. But school leaders in the conducted research areas are preparing, Participating stakeholders and evaluating their work moderately. Hence still improving the activities of planning in the school is very essential.

The role of school leaders in setting goal and developing vision as the major standard of effectiveness of school leaders was analyzed. It was found out that setting goal and developing vision found to be moderately executed. However it was also identified that the leader motivation and encouragement of students and teachers for the best performance was not done to the desired level. Hence, still it is found that there is lack of setting and developing vision of the school as expected quality and standard. Therefore, from this one can conclude that the direction of school vision and goals was having gap strategically linked with the national direction.

Principals are expected to provide opportunities for teachers, staff members, students, parents and community members participate in school decision making for the success of teaching learning concerning this, the finding of the study showed that principals have moderately contribution towards strengthening participatory decision making, this is insufficient or inadequate in establishing measures regarding how communicate problems and there is gap in decision making or taking measures to the quality of teaching learning activities. Therefore active participation of school community and stakeholders is very crucial for implementing quality education and leadership.

One of the most important roles to be played by school leaders is instructional leadership role, majority of school leaders created favorable conditions for school community members more active participate in problem solving and academic activities. Moreover they tried to encourage those teachers who implemented the curriculum effectively by providing moral support. In contrast, some of the school leaders have not worked further for the involvement of parents in curriculum development. Since curriculum development is the concern of all communities, school leaders should improve their leadership role to involve parents on the curriculum development issues. Lack of training in school leadership ,adequate resource, work over load, working with parents and the community, sharing the problems of school leadership by higher officials and ability to give professional assistance and guidance to teachers to enable them realize instructional objectives were major challenges identified by most of participants. What does it mean to educational leaders and higher officials? It clearly means that in order to give

quality education for students, the stake holders and concerned bodies must intensively doing and focus on those challenges of school leadership.

5.3 RECOMMENDATIONS

School community and the society at large believe that behind all successes and failures of the school, the school leadership role is there. Secondary schools need to promote effective leadership at all grade levels in the school in order to achieve educational goals by mobilizing and using resources efficiently”.

This section presents the recommendations in accordance with the main research aim and the last of the six conclusions of this study (5.2). Thus, on the basis of the study results, the following recommendations are made:

1. The sub city education office should select and assign qualified secondary school principals and vice principals on the basis of their experience and academic merits for the improvement of school in general and effectiveness of teachers and school leaders in particular
2. The city education bureau and the sub city are encouraged to prepare in-service and pre-service training that will enhance the principals’ skills on school leadership.
3. Setting clear goal and objective and making them clear to all communities and influencing communities for its achievement is the responsibility of school leaders. So city education bureau and sub city education office must give continuous training on how to formulate and implement strategic planning, setting school goals and objectives and school leaders working with staff and parents to implement the school plan.
4. The active participation of stakeholders in school leadership creates conducive atmosphere and development. So school leaders need to build productive relationships with parents and the wider community, to carry out plans every activity in the school.
5. School leaders in the sub city must involve School community in decision making. This will help to create participatory management within the school. Participative management can encourage the establishment of team work with in schools. When all school

community is united it becomes very easy for the school leaders to exercise his educational leadership role within the school.

To sum up, further study and due attention should be given to school leadership by responsible bodies so as to address the challenges more adequately and to give attention for the future betterment of the coming generation.

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